

WHY DO STUDENTS INVOLVE IN LEISURE-SPORT INDUSTRIES? USING THE STIMULUS-ORGANISM-RESPONSE MODEL TO UNDERSTAND CAREER ENGAGEMENT IN LEISURE-SPORT INDUSTRIES

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Abstract

Leisure-sport is a professional industry that promotes people's physical and mental health in the world. It is important to train and retain professionals to enhance service quality and industrial development. The purpose of this study is to identify the antecedents of career engagement in leisure-sport industries by using stimulus (learning engagement)-organism (professional identity and career self-efficiency)-response (career engagement) model from students' perspectives who are studying in the department of leisure-sport. Quantitative method was adopted to address the study issues. Questionnaire was developed by the researcher according to previous studies. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents who are junior and senior students in Department of Sport management and Department of Recreational Management in National Taiwan University of Sport. A total of one hundred and forty-three copied questionnaires were collected, the effective response rate was 91.6%. The collected data were analyzed by descriptive statistics and partial least squares structural equations. The study findings indicated that students' learning engagement does not significantly influence their career engagement in leisure-sport industries. However, learning engagement has indirectly significant effects on career engagement via professional identity and career self-efficiency, which are full mediators in the model. Accordingly, increasing students' professional identity and career self-efficiency can contribute to their career engagement in leisure-sport industries.

Keywords: Stimulus-Organism-Response Model, Sports And Leisure Industry, Sport Management, Career Planning.

JEL Classification: [I23, L83, J24]

INTRODUCTION

The sports and leisure industry has gradually become a key driver of the economy in developed countries, as it not only enhances the quality of life for citizens but also lays a solid economic foundation for nations. Aligning with this global trend, Taiwan has actively promoted the development of its sports and leisure industry. The government has formulated guidance strategies and allocated funding for the industry's development, while also encouraging private enterprises to invest in it (Sports Administration, Ministry of Education, 2020). Driven by these relevant policies, the sports and leisure industry in Taiwan has achieved remarkable results. According to data from the Annual Report on the Sports Industry (Sports Administration, Ministry of Education, 2020), the total revenue of Taiwan's sports industry reached NT\$964.3 billion in 2018— a staggering 615% increase compared to NT\$134.9 billion in 2015.

Meanwhile, the number of employees in the industry surged from 64,054 to 173,913, representing a 172% growth in employment. These figures indicate a growing demand for professional talents in the sports and leisure industry. To meet this human resource demand, 36 colleges and universities in Taiwan have established relevant departments (Ministry of Education, 2021). These institutions design educational curricula for the sports and leisure industry and provide students with internship opportunities in the sector, aiming to cultivate more professionals in the field, facilitate the integration of graduates into the industry, and enhance the competitiveness of these talents. For industry operators, the cultivation of professionals by educational institutions not only reduces business operation costs but also shortens the time required to develop the specialized talents needed by the industry (Huang, Yao, & Li, 2020). Therefore, the willingness of graduates to engage in careers within the sports and leisure industry is of great significance to the industry's development.

Career engagement willingness contributes to individuals' work effectiveness and promotes the economic prosperity of industries (Jiang, Jiang, & Nielsen, 2020). It refers to the degree to which employees voluntarily commit to their career development (Hirschi, Freund, & Herrmann, 2014). A high level of career engagement willingness among individuals is conducive to setting future work goals, enhancing work skills and capabilities, accumulating work experience, and developing personal potential (Claes & Ruiz-Quintanilla, 1998). Numerous previous studies have focused on exploring the factors influencing individuals' career engagement willingness, including career attitudes (De Vos & Soens, 2008), self-identity (Hirschi, Freund, & Herrmann, 2014), self-efficacy (He & Yang, 2011), career satisfaction (Liang, 1999), industry identity (Su, 2018), personal interests (Su, 2018), and learning engagement (Chen, Tseng, Hu, Tseng, & Wang, 2017). Among these factors, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and learning engagement exert significant impacts on college students' career development. For instance, Su's (2018) study found that college students' interest in the marine industry and their identity with their academic department had a significant influence on their willingness to engage in careers within the marine industry. He et al. (2011), in a study on students majoring in catering management, discovered that improving career self-efficacy during internships could positively affect students' career engagement behaviors. Additionally, Chen et al. (2017) reported that the higher the level of learning engagement among students majoring in healthcare management, the more proactive they were in their professional field. Against this backdrop, this study examines the career engagement willingness of college students majoring in sports and leisure-related programs, with a specific focus on three key factors: learning engagement, departmental identity, and career self-efficacy.

The "Stimulus-Organism-Response" model (SOR model), first proposed by Mehrabian & Russell (1974), primarily explores whether personal emotions and environmental factors stimulate consumers' personal perceptions or consumption behaviors. Within the SOR model, factors such as the environment and personal values influence an individual's motivation or awareness; driven by this motivation, the individual then exhibits responsive behaviors. For example, businesses may use marketing tactics such as product packaging and advertising (Stimulus), which in turn trigger consumers' desire to shop (Organism), and ultimately lead to

consumers' behavior of purchasing the product (Response). In previous studies, the SOR model has mostly been applied to consumer-related topics. For instance, Ke (2018) applied it to research on digital reading, and Lai (2020) used it to study green marketing. However, no research has yet applied this model to issues related to career engagement. Against this backdrop, this study adopts the SOR model to examine whether the learning engagement (Stimulus) of college students majoring in sports and leisure-related programs exerts an impact on their career self-efficacy and departmental identity (Organism), which in turn determines their willingness to engage in careers within the sports and leisure industry in the future (Response). This study takes the SOR model as its theoretical foundation and verifies and analyzes the constructs of students' departmental identity, learning engagement, career self-efficacy, and career engagement. It is expected that this research will make contributions to the field of the sports and leisure industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The "Stimulus-Organism-Response" Model

The early consumer behavior model (CBM) was regarded as an input-to-output process, also known as the I+O model. Scholars argued that consumers, under the assumption of rational shopping, would exhibit behaviors such as purchasing or spending (output) due to factors like economic or financial conditions (input). In the mid-1960s, as the importance of internal individual factors gradually gained recognition, the I+O model was extended to form the current "Stimulus-Organism-Response" model (SOR model), which primarily emphasizes the correlation of internal factors between stimulus and response (Jacob Jacoby, 2002). In Ke's (2018) study, the SOR model was used to explore the relationships between perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude, perceived value, and behavioral intention toward choosing digital reading. Lai (2020) applied the SOR model to analyze the influence of consumption value, perceived innovative characteristics, and market potential on the willingness to adopt green innovative products. The aforementioned studies all focus on consumer-related issues, with few targeting students as research subjects. Therefore, to fill this gap, this study uses the "Stimulus-Organism-Response" model as its foundation to analyze the relationships among students' departmental identity, learning engagement, career self-efficacy, and career engagement.

Stimulus: Learning Engagement

Learning engagement refers to the process of behaviors, thinking, and feelings generated by students during their learning (Kuh, 2009). It also describes the situation where students interact with peers and teachers, or actively participate in school activities, enabling themselves to think deeply and learn proactively (Wang, 2011). Learning engagement plays a crucial role in students' learning journeys, serving as the foundation for learners' emotional and cognitive experiences (Mosenthal, 1999). Lai and Wu (2022) pointed out that teachers who are willing to motivate students and provide autonomous support are key factors influencing students' learning engagement. In other words, when teachers take the initiative to support students, it not only enhances their learning motivation but also promotes their learning engagement. A

study by Yeh, Wang, and Yeh (2020) found a positive correlation between students' achievement motivation and their engagement in project-based learning. Specifically, higher levels of learning enthusiasm, perseverance, and sense of accomplishment among students can enhance their learning engagement behaviors.

Astin (1993) discovered that students' participation in diverse activities and increased interactions with teachers and peers have extensive positive impacts on their cognitive and emotional development. In other words, higher learning engagement among college students leads to more proactive behaviors, such as taking the initiative to understand knowledge related to their academic department and making clearer choices regarding future employment. Zhang, Lin, and Zhou (2012) argued that learning engagement centers on students and further analyzed students' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions to facilitate the measurement of the learning engagement process. Therefore, this study incorporates learning engagement as a research variable, dividing it into three sub-variables: cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, and behavioral engagement. The research hypotheses are as follows:

H1: Learning engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant impact on departmental identity.

H2: Learning engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant impact on career self-efficacy.

H3: Learning engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant impact on career engagement.

Organism: Departmental Identity and Career Self-Efficacy

Departmental identity refers to the state where students perceive themselves as part of their academic department, position themselves as members of the department, and identify with this status without feeling inferior (Finn, 1989; Voelkl, 1997). In a study on healthcare management students, Chen et al. (2017) found that demographic characteristics, departmental administrative support, attitudes and communication of departmental administrators, personal qualities of departmental teachers, teaching methods of departmental teachers, and classroom facilities exerted a positive mediating effect on departmental engagement and career attitudes through departmental identity. In other words, various resources provided by the department help enhance students' identification with the department, encourage them to actively engage in their studies, and incline them to choose related careers in the future.

A study on three departments—International Business, Business Administration, and Accounting & Financial Finance—revealed that improved departmental identity not only strengthens students' academic engagement and interpersonal interactions with peers and teachers but also influences their choice of career in the field they study (Wang, Yue, Huang, & Kang, 2020). However, existing research lacks studies on career engagement and departmental identity among students in sports and leisure-related departments. Applying departmental identity to predict the career choices of students in sports and leisure departments

could promote the development of the sports and leisure industry. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Departmental identity of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant impact on career engagement.

Career self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their confidence, determination, and ability to address career-related issues. From the perspective of social cognitive theory, career development is often influenced by self-efficacy (Betz & Hackett, 1981). The level of career self-efficacy affects an individual's career exploration behaviors and may even cause anxiety about career choices (Bandura, 2000). He et al. (2011) studied college students in catering management departments, examining the relationships between variables such as students' satisfaction with on-campus learning, satisfaction with off-campus internships, career self-efficacy, and career choices, finding that career self-efficacy plays a mediating role in career choices.

Ren's (2005) research indicated that individuals with higher career self-efficacy have better compatibility with their future career choices. Thus, career self-efficacy is crucial for graduates' future career decisions. This study uses career self-efficacy to explore whether students in sports-related departments can confidently and competently solve career-related problems without fear, and whether they will choose careers in the sports industry. The research hypotheses are as follows:

H5: Career self-efficacy of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant impact on career engagement.

H6: Learning engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant indirect impact on career engagement through departmental identity.

H7: Learning engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan has a significant indirect impact on career engagement through career self-efficacy.

Response: Career Engagement

Career engagement refers to the degree to which employees voluntarily commit to their career development. Gaining job satisfaction and sufficient self-confidence in work is conducive to the willingness to engage in one's career (Hirschi et al., 2014). Su's (2018) study found that primary school students' greater interest in marine issues positively influences their willingness to engage in marine careers. He et al. (2011), in their research on college students in catering management departments, discovered that students' learning experiences affect their career self-efficacy, which in turn determines their future career paths.

Huang et al. (2022) studied internships in tourism-related departments and found that organizational development support provided by internship institutions—such as employee training courses—not only enhances students' career fit, personal values, and abilities but also motivates their willingness to engage in their careers. In other words, if students in sports and leisure-related departments can identify their interests, set career goals, and gain experience

through internships, they will be more likely to voluntarily engage in the workplace in the future, promoting the growth of the sports and leisure industry.

Figure 1: Research Hypothesis Model

METHODS

Research Design

This study aims to explore the relationships among learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement of students in sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan. It uses the "Stimulus-Organism-Response Model" to construct the research framework and adopts a questionnaire survey method to address the research issues. The research instruments are developed by referencing definitions from literature related to learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement, with data collected through physical questionnaires. After excluding invalid questionnaires, data analysis will be conducted using descriptive statistics and partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM), followed by the compilation of research results and discussions.

Research Subjects and Data Collection

Pilot Questionnaire

The pilot study targeted students from the Department of Sports Business Management and the Department of Leisure Sports at National Taiwan University of Sport. First- and second-year students were excluded from the survey, while third- and fourth-year students from these two departments were selected as research subjects using purposive sampling. A collective questionnaire survey was conducted: with the assistance of classroom teachers, the researcher personally distributed physical questionnaires in classes and collected them on-site. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed, and 155 were returned. Among these, 13 questionnaires were excluded due to completely identical responses to all questions, resulting in 142 valid questionnaires, with a final valid response rate of 91.6%.

Formal Questionnaire

The subjects of this study are students from sports and leisure-related departments in Taiwan. According to the List of Universities and Colleges in Taiwan (Ministry of Education, 2021), there are 36 institutions offering sports and leisure-related departments, distributed as follows: 10 in northern Taiwan, 6 in central Taiwan, 17 in southern Taiwan, 1 in eastern Taiwan, and 2 on outlying islands. This study will use random sampling to select 15 institutions from these 36, including 4 in the north, 3 in the center, 6 in the south, 1 in the east, and 1 on outlying islands. Quota sampling will then be used to distribute questionnaires: 26% in the north, 20% in the center, 40% in the south, 7% in the east, and 7% on outlying islands. Finally, purposive sampling will be employed to select third- and fourth-year undergraduates from relevant departments, excluding first- and second-year undergraduates and graduate students. A mail survey method will be used: the researcher will contact teachers from each department to assist in distributing physical questionnaires in classes, who will then mail the completed questionnaires back. A total of 750 questionnaires are planned to be distributed, with 200 in the north, 150 in the center, 300 in the south, 50 in the east, and 50 on outlying islands. The distribution is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Quota of Number of Departments, Proportions, and Questionnaires by Region

Region	Number of Departments	%	Number of Questionnaires
Northern	4	26%	200
Central	3	20%	150
Southern	6	40%	300
Eastern	1	7%	50
Outlying Islands	1	7%	50
TT		750	

Research Instruments

The scales for learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement in this study were developed based on definitions from relevant research. Learning Engagement: Drawing on the definition of learning engagement by Yeh et al. (2020), 12 items were developed, covering three dimensions: behavioral engagement (4 items), emotional engagement (4 items), and cognitive engagement (4 items). Departmental Identity: Adopting a single-dimensional structure based on the definitions of departmental identity by Wang et al. (2020) and Chen et al. (2017), 9 items were developed.

Career Self-Efficacy: Based on the definition of career self-efficacy by Zhan (2013), 21 items were developed, including five dimensions: self-understanding assessment (5 items), problem-solving ability (5 items), career information collection (4 items), future planning (4 items), and goal selection and decision-making (3 items). Career Engagement: Using a single-dimensional structure according to the definition of career engagement by Su (2018), 9 items were developed. All items for learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement were measured using a 7-point Likert scale, where "Strongly Agree" corresponds to 7 points and "Strongly Disagree" corresponds to 1 point. The scale items are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Items of Learning Engagement, Departmental Identity, Career Self-Efficacy, and Career Engagement Scales

Variable	Items
Learning Engagement	I will...
	1. Take responsibility for collecting materials for class presentations (L1)
	2. Actively engage in class presentations (L2)
	3. Rest only after completing a section of class assignments (L3)
	4. Be so absorbed in solving learning problems from class that I forget meals and sleep, and feel uneasy if not solved (L4)
	5. Make plans in advance for class presentations (L5)
	6. Note mistakes made in class presentations and avoid repeating them (L6)
	7. Record key details from classes (L7)
	8. Search for additional class-related information and record it (L8)
	I like to...
	9. Spend time on class presentations (L9)
	10. Discuss class presentation issues with classmates (L10)
11. Proactively explore unfamiliar content in class presentations (L11)	
12. Courageously admit mistakes when I make them in class presentations (L12)	
Departmental Identity	The professional field I study...
	1. Belongs to a continuously developing industry (D1)
	2. Has unlimited future opportunities (D2)
	3. Is a key driver of future economic development (D3)
	4. Offers higher salaries than other fields (D4)
	I believe that...
	5. Students in my department perform as well as those in other departments (D5)
	6. I feel proud when others praise my department (D6)
	7. The expertise gained from my department is useful (D7)
8. The expertise of my department is worth my investment in learning (D8)	
9. I am a member of my department (D9)	
Career Self-Efficacy	I clearly understand what I want to pursue in the future regarding...
	1. Job content (S1)
	2. Work environment (S2)
	3. Job title (S3)
	4. Career-related information (S4)
	5. Career enthusiasm (S5)
	Even when facing setbacks or problems, I will...
	6. Adhere to my life goals (S6)
	7. Think and search for information to solve problems (S7)
	8. Achieve the goal of studying in my major as planned (S8)
	9. Seek advice from others (S9)
	10. Find ways to solve problems (S10)
	I can identify...
	11. Which companies hire graduates in the sports and leisure industry (S11)
	12. Employment market trends in the sports and leisure industry over the next 5 years (S12)
13. Average annual income for the sports and leisure industry jobs I want to pursue (S13)	
14. Jobs that match my professional skills (S14)	
I will...	
15. Consult teachers about information on job opportunities in the sports industry (S15)	

	16. Take courses that are beneficial for future employment in the sports industry (S16)
	17. Strive to move toward self-defined goals (S17)
	18. Use resources from the counseling center to help with my employment (S18)
	I am able to..
	19. Persuade my family to support my decision to work in the sports and leisure industry (S19)
	20. Decide on the job I want to pursue in the future (S20)
	21. Choose a job that matches my ideal lifestyle (S21)
	I am willing to...
	1. Work in the sports and leisure industry (C1)
	2. Be proud of working in the sports and leisure industry (C2)
Career Engagement	3. Contribute to the sports and leisure industry (C3)
	4. Enhance my confidence in the sports and leisure industry (C4)
	5. Take the sports and leisure industry as my main career development path (C5)

Expert Validity

After formulating the preliminary scale, this study invited 2 experts in sports industry-related fields to conduct expert validity verification, specifically professors in sports-related management fields from National Chin-Yi University of Technology and National Dong Hwa University. An online questionnaire was sent to the experts for evaluation.

The experts scored the content applicability of each item in the scale on a 1-4 point scale, with the scoring criteria as follows: 1 point for "very inapplicable"; 2 points for "inapplicable" (indicating the item is not applicable); 3 points for "applicable" (indicating the item is applicable but requires slight modification); and 4 points for "very applicable" (indicating high applicability with no need for modification). Items scoring 3 points or higher were adopted.

The Content Validity Index (CVI) for each item was calculated by dividing the number of experts who rated the item as 3 (applicable) or 4 (very applicable) by the total number of experts. Items with a CVI of 0.8 or higher were retained. For items with a score of 2 or lower, experts were invited to provide revision suggestions, and the scale was modified accordingly. After calculation, the CVI for the content applicability of all items in this study was 1, so no items were deleted, and only minor revisions were made to the wording of the items (Hsieh, 2015).

Data Analysis

Pilot Questionnaire Analysis

This study used descriptive statistics in the Chinese version of SPSS 18.0 statistical software to analyze sample background information, item analysis, exploratory factor analysis, and reliability and validity analysis. The partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) in SMART-PLS 3.0 was used to analyze the results of the preliminary structural model.

Formal Questionnaire Analysis

For the formal questionnaire, descriptive statistics in the Chinese version of SPSS 18.0 statistical software will be used to analyze sample background information. Furthermore, the partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) in SMART-PLS 3.0 will be used to test the reliability and validity of learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-

efficacy, and career engagement, as well as to analyze the structural model, in order to verify the hypotheses of this study.

Research Ethics

To adhere to research ethics, this study will conduct an anonymous questionnaire survey to ensure that respondents' personal information cannot be identified. All research subjects will be over 20 years old and can decide whether to participate in the study voluntarily; those under 20 will be excluded. This study will use a mail survey method, with the assistance of teachers from each department to distribute physical questionnaires in class. Before distributing the questionnaires, respondents will be informed of their rights and the purpose of the study. Respondents will participate voluntarily after understanding and agreeing, and there will be no teacher-student conflict of interest. If respondents are unwilling to participate or withdraw from the study during the process, their rights at school will not be impaired, nor will the results be adversely affected. The collected data will only be reviewed and analyzed by researchers and will not be used for any purpose other than academic research. Researchers will destroy the data independently after the study is published.

RESULTS

Pilot Questionnaire

The analysis of sample background information showed the following:

Gender: Female students accounted for a slightly higher proportion (57.6%) than male students (42.4%). Grade: Fourth-year students (52.5%) were slightly more than third-year students (47.5%). Admission Method: "Application-based admission" was the most common (23.9%), followed by "Star Program admission" (22.5%). Internship Experience: More students had participated in internships (68.3%) than those who had not (31.7%). Department Type: Students majoring in "Sports Industry Management" (61.2%) were slightly more than those in "Leisure Sports Management" (38.8%). Details are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Analysis of Sample Background Information

	Variable	ariaFrequency	%	Cumulative (%)
Gender	Male	59	42.4	42.4
	Female	80	57.6	100
Grade	Third-year	66	47.5	47.5
	Fourth-year	73	52.5	100
Admission Method	Star Program admission	31	22.5	22.5
	Application-based admission	33	23.9	46.4
	Recommendation-based admission	23	16.7	63
	Independent enrollment	23	16.7	79.7
Internship Experience	Unified college entrance examination admission	23	20.3	100
	Yes	84	68.3	68.3
	No	39	31.7	100
Department Type	Sports Industry Management	85	61.2	61.2
	Leisure Sports Management	54	38.8	100

Item Analysis

For the scales of learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement in this study, the correlation coefficients for the homogeneity test were all above .300 and reached a significant level. Additionally, the extreme group tests for all scale items were significant. Therefore, all items were retained. Details are presented in Table 3-1, Table 3-2, Table 3-3, and Table 3-4.

Table 3-1: Summary of Homogeneity Test and Extreme Group Test for the Learning Engagement Scale

Item	t-value	Item-Total Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
I will...			
1. Take responsibility for collecting materials for class presentations	-9.496*	.686	Retained
2. Actively engage in class presentations	-13.267*	.707	Retained
3. Rest only after completing a section of class assignments	-11.759*	.717	Retained
4. Be so absorbed in solving learning problems from class that I forget meals and sleep, and feel uneasy if not solved	-5.288*	.381	Retained
5. Make plans in advance for class presentations	-9.514*	.665	Retained
6. Note mistakes made in class presentations and avoid repeating them	-10.574*	.757	Retained
7. Record key details from classes	-8.945*	.652	Retained
8. Search for additional class-related information and record it	-12.100*	.665	Retained
I like to...			
9. Spend time on class presentations	-9.102*	.677	Retained
10. Discuss class presentation issues with classmates	-6.722*	.659	Retained
11. Proactively explore unfamiliar content in class presentations	-12.520*	.722	Retained
12. Courageously admit mistakes when I make them in class presentations	-9.177*	.663	Retained
*p < .05			

Table 3-2: Summary of Homogeneity Test and Extreme Group Test for the Departmental Identity Scale

Item	t-value	Item-Total Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
The professional field I study...			
1. Belongs to a continuously developing industry	-7.948*	.564	Retained
2. Has unlimited future opportunities	-13.338*	.774	Retained
3. Is a key driver of future economic development	-11.046*	.752	Retained
4. Offers higher salaries than other fields	-8.567*	.534	Retained
I believe that...			
5. Students in my department perform as well as those in other departments	-12.648*	.715	Retained
6. I feel proud when others praise my department	-10.467*	.727	Retained

7. The expertise gained from my department is useful	-15.610*	.758	Retained
8. The expertise of my department is worth my investment in learning	-18.838*	.768	Retained
9. I am a member of my department	-10.293*	.675	Retained
*p< .05			

Table 3-3: Summary of Homogeneity Test and Extreme Group Test for the Career Self-Efficacy Scale

Item	t-value	Item-Total Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
I clearly understand what I want to pursue in the future:			
1. Job content	-11.542*	.906	Retained
2. Work environment	-15.039*	.891	Retained
3. Job title	-10.946*	.869	Retained
4. Job-related information	-12.554*	.903	Retained
5. Passion for the job	-14.294*	.758	Retained
When facing setbacks or problems, I will...			
6. Stick to my life goals	-12.647*	.831	Retained
7. Think about and search for information related to problem-solving	-12.651*	.839	Retained
8. Achieve the goal of studying in the chosen department as planned	-9.099*	.744	Retained
9. Ask others for advice	-9.887*	.728	Retained
10. Find ways to solve problems	-11.777*	.803	Retained
I can find out...			
11. Which companies hire graduates in the sports and leisure industry	-9.109*	.708	Retained
12. Employment market trends in the sports and leisure industry in the next 5 years	-12.142*	.813	Retained
13. Average annual income of the sports and leisure industry jobs I want to take	-10.552*	.813	Retained
14. Jobs that match my professional skills	-10.119*	.659	Retained
I will...			
15. Consult teachers about information related to job opportunities in the sports industry	-10.155*	.753	Retained
16. Take elective courses that are beneficial for future employment in the sports industry	-11.139*	.756	Retained
17. Strive to move toward self-defined goals	-12.353*	.666	Retained
18. Use resources from the counseling center to help with my employment	-9.120*	.654	Retained
I am able to...			
19. Persuade my family to support my decision to work in the sports and leisure industry	-10.241*	.690	Retained
20. Decide on the job I want to take in the future	-8.652*	.783	Retained
21. Choose a job that matches my ideal lifestyle	-9.098*	.724	Retained
*p< .05			

Table 3-4: Summary of Homogeneity Test and Extreme Group Test for the Career Engagement Scale

Item	t-value	Item-Total Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
I am willing to...			
1. Work in the sports and leisure industry	-14.236*	.865	Retained
2. Take pride in working in the sports and leisure industry	-16.782*	.879	Retained
3. Contribute my efforts to the sports and leisure industry	-18.732*	.877	Retained
4. Enhance my confidence in the sports and leisure industry	-19.246*	.881	Retained
5. Take the sports and leisure industry as my main career development	-19.718*	.864	Retained
*p < .05			

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Learning Engagement Scale

A total of four exploratory factor analyses were conducted on the learning engagement scale in this study. The chi-square values of the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ranged from 1013.196* to 559.970*, all reaching statistical significance (*p < 0.05), indicating the presence of common factors in the correlation matrix. The KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) values ranged from 0.868 to 0.845, demonstrating good suitability of the learning engagement scale for factor analysis. Three items were eliminated during the four rounds of exploratory factor analysis, namely "Proactively explore unfamiliar content in class presentations", "Actively engage in class presentations", and "Take responsibility for collecting materials for class presentations". Detailed descriptions are presented in Table 3-5.

Table 3-5: Summary of the First Three Rounds of Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Learning Engagement Scale

Round of Analysis	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	KMO Value	Eliminated Item	Eliminated Item
1st Round	1013.20*	.868	Proactively explore unfamiliar content in class presentations	Proactively explore unfamiliar content in class presentations
2nd Round	863.96*	.847	Actively engage in class presentations	Actively engage in class presentations
3rd Round	652.26*	.853	Take responsibility for collecting materials for class presentations	Take responsibility for collecting materials for class presentations
*p < .05				

After the four rounds of exploratory factor analysis mentioned above, a total of three items were eliminated. For the fourth exploratory factor analysis, the chi-square value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was 559.970*, which reached a significant level (*p < 0.05). The KMO value was 0.845, indicating good suitability for factor analysis. The analysis results showed that the learning engagement scale was divided into three factors, with eigenvalues of 3.008, 2.109,

and 1.378 respectively, and the cumulative explained variance was 72.186%. These three factors are consistent with the theoretical framework of learning engagement in this study; therefore, they were named "Cognitive Engagement", "Emotional Engagement", and "Behavioral Engagement" respectively, encompassing a total of 9 items. Details are presented in Table 3-6 and Table 3-7.

Table 3-6: Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity Chi-Square Value and KMO Value for the Learning Engagement Scale

Index	Value
KMO Value	.845
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity Chi-Square Value	559.970
Degrees of Freedom (df)	36
Significance (Sig.)	.000

Table 3-7: Summary of the Fourth Round of Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Learning Engagement Scale

Item	Cognitive Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Behavioral Engagement
I will:			
1. Make plans in advance before class presentations	.820	.162	.080
2. Pay attention to mistakes made in my class presentations and avoid them next time	.811	.328	.103
3. Record key details in class	.769	.139	.126
4. Search for additional information related to the class and record it	.707	0.221	.315
I like to:			
5. Discuss class presentation issues with classmates	.134	.907	.043
6. Devote time to class presentations	.229	.757	.305
7. Have the courage to admit mistakes when I make them in class presentations	.485	.654	.052
I will:			
8. Be so absorbed in solving learning problems in class that I forget to eat or sleep, and feel uneasy if they are not solved	.113	.097	.926
9. Only take a break after finishing a section of class assignments	.517	.273	.540
Eigenvalue	3.008	2.109	1.378
Explained Variance (%)	33.427	23.430	15.310
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	33.427	56.857	72.168

Career Self-Efficacy Scale

A total of three exploratory factor analyses were conducted on the career self-efficacy scale in this study. The chi-square values of Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity ranged from 2675.546* to 2422.901*, all reaching statistical significance (*p < 0.05), indicating the presence of common factors in the correlation matrix. The KMO values ranged from 0.931 to 0.923, demonstrating good suitability of the career self-efficacy scale for factor analysis. Two items were eliminated during the three rounds of exploratory factor analysis, namely "Strive to move toward self-

defined goals" and "Jobs that match my professional skills". Detailed descriptions are presented in Table 3-8.

Table 3-8: Summary of the First Two Rounds of Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Career Self-Efficacy Scale

Round of Analysis	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	KMO Value	Eliminated Item	Reason for Elimination
1st Round	2675.55*	.931	Strive to move toward self-defined goals	All factor loadings of the item were lower than 0.5 (insufficient factor correlation)
2nd Round	2549.63*	.927	Jobs that match my professional skills	Factor loadings on Factor 3 (.587) and Factor 4 (.507) were similar (cross-loading)

*p < .05

After the three rounds of exploratory factor analysis mentioned above, a total of two items were eliminated. For the third exploratory factor analysis, the chi-square value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was 2422.901*, which reached a significant level (*p < .05). The KMO value was 0.923, indicating good suitability for factor analysis. The analysis results showed that the career self-efficacy scale was divided into five factors, with eigenvalues of 4.437, 3.560, 2.596, 2.406, and 2.397 respectively, and the cumulative explained variance was 81.035%. These five factors are consistent with the theoretical framework of career self-efficacy in this study; therefore, they were named "Self-Understanding Assessment", "Problem-Solving Ability", "Career Information Collection", "Future Planning", and "Goal Selection & Decision-Making" respectively, encompassing a total of 19 items. Details are presented in Table 3-9 and Table 3-10.

Table 3-9: Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Chi-Square Value and KMO Value for the Career Self-Efficacy Scale

Index	Value
KMO Value	.923
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Chi-Square Value	2422.901*
Degrees of Freedom (df)	171

Table 3-10: Summary of the Third Round of Exploratory Factor Analysis for the Career Self-Efficacy Scale

Item	Self-Understanding Assessment	Problem-Solving Ability	Goal Selection & Decision-Making	Career Information Collection	Future Planning
I clearly understand what I want to pursue in the future...					
1. Job content	.884	.198	.113	.210	.155
2. Job title	.868	.198	.061	.193	.170
3. Job-related information	.839	.285	.135	.268	.116
4. Work environment	.826	.224	.206	.236	.197
5. Passion for the job	.719	.298	.377	.033	.132
When facing setbacks or problems, I will...					

6. Ask others for advice	.172	.756	.183	-.007	.391
7. Find ways to solve problems	.271	.747	.319	-.010	.313
8. Think about and search for information related to problem-solving	.324	.747	.184	.352	.151
9. Achieve the goal of studying in the chosen department as planned	.253	.717	.290	.274	.000
10. Stick to my life goals	.345	.717	.303	.277	.103
I am able to...					
11. Decide on the job I want to take in the future	.215	.282	.836	.018	.212
12. Choose a job that matches my ideal lifestyle	.191	.383	.716	.343	.056
13. Persuade my family to support my decision to work in the sports and leisure industry	.141	.301	.681	.146	.331
I can find out...					
14. Average annual income of the sports and leisure industry jobs I want to take	.451	.148	.155	.719	.254
15. Employment market trends in the sports and leisure industry in the next 5 years	.389	.247	.053	.714	.367
16. Which companies hire graduates in the sports and leisure industry	.174	.190	.238	.698	.388
I will...					
17. Use resources from the counseling center to help with my employment	.218	.243	.064	.233	.751
18. Take elective courses that are beneficial for future employment in the sports industry	.157	.199	.292	.319	.710
19. Consult teachers about information related to job opportunities in the sports industry	.219	.111	.428	.330	.644
Eigenvalue	4.437	3.560	2.596	2.406	2.397
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	23.351	18.739	13.663	12.665	12.618
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	23.351	42.090	55.753	68.418	81.035

Reliability, Validity, and Model Fit Analysis

This study used internal consistency analysis, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) to test the scale reliability. The Cronbach's α coefficient is an indicator for determining the internal consistency of a scale. In this study, the Cronbach's α coefficients for learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement ranged from .900 to .928, indicating good internal consistency (Wu & Tu, 2012). The composite reliability of the four variables ranged from .919 to .965, suggesting a high degree of intercorrelation among the items of each variable (Huang, 2009). In terms of average variance extracted (AVE), the values for learning engagement (.511), departmental identity (.559), career self-efficacy (.536), and career engagement (.846) were all higher than .500. This indicates that more than 50% of the variance explained by each variable comes from the items

themselves (Chen, 2007). Overall, the scales used in this study demonstrated good reliability. Details are presented in Table 3-11.

Table 3-11: Factor Loadings and Reliability Analysis

Variable	Item	Factor Loading	Cronbach's α	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Learning Engagement	L3	.761	.910	.925	.511
	L4	.464			
	L5	.691			
	L6	.782			
	L7	.643			
	L8	.714			
	L9	.711			
	L10	.661			
Departmental Identity	L12	.758	.900	.919	.559
	D1	.643			
	D2	.783			
	D3	.688			
	D4	.647			
	D5	.779			
	D6	.746			
	D7	.840			
Career Self-Efficacy	D8	.848	.956	.960	.536
	D9	.723			
	S1	.750			
	S2	.795			
	S3	.719			
	S4	.784			
	S5	.734			
	S6	.792			
	S7	.801			
	S8	.697			
	S9	.677			
	S10	.642			
	S11	.709			
	S12	.779			
	S13	.768			
Career Engagement	S15	.744	.955	.965	.846
	S16	.722			
	S18	.648			
	S19	.683			
	S20	.676			
Career Engagement	S21	.712	.914		
	C1	.911			
	C2	.921			
	C3	.925			
	C4	.928			
*p<.05					

Convergent validity and discriminant validity are regarded as the basis for testing scale validity. Huang (2006) argued that the factor loadings of observed variables are values used to determine the presence of convergent validity. A factor loading higher than 0.500 indicates a significant level, meaning the observed variable can effectively reflect the latent variable. In this study, the factor loadings of all items for learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement were higher than 0.500 (see Table 3-11), and all reached a significant level. This indicates that the items of the scales in this study have good convergent validity. For discriminant validity, the correlation coefficients between individual variables in this study were all smaller than the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) of each variable (see Table 3-12). This confirms the presence of discriminant validity among the variables in this study (Gaski & Nevin, 1985).

Table 3-12: Discriminant Validity

Variable	Learning Engagement	Career Self-Efficacy	Departmental Identity	Career Engagement
Learning Engagement	.715			
Career Self-Efficacy	.659	.732		
Departmental Identity	.551	.534	.747	
Career Engagement	.493	.588	.638	.920

In the model fit analysis, Goodness of Fit (GoF) is a key model fit indicator for partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). The calculation formula for GoF is as follows:

$$GoF = \sqrt{\text{average AVE} \times \text{average } R^2}$$

A GoF value above 0.36 indicates a high level of model fit, a value between 0.25 and 0.35 indicates a moderate level, and a value between 0.10 and 0.24 indicates an acceptable level. A GoF value below 0.10 means the model has poor fit (Akter, D'Ambra, & Ray, 2011). The calculated GoF value of the model in this study was 0.763, indicating that the model incorporating learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement has a high level of fit.

Structural Model Analysis

The results of the structural model analysis on learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement of students in Taiwan's sports and leisure-related departments (see Figure 2), Learning engagement had a significant positive impact on both departmental identity ($\beta = .551^*$, $p < .05$) and career self-efficacy ($\beta = .659$, $*p < .05$), but no significant impact on career engagement ($\beta = .02$, $p > .05$). Departmental identity had a significant positive impact on career engagement ($\beta = .445^*$, $p < .05$), and career self-efficacy also had a significant positive impact on career engagement ($\beta = .331$, $*p < .05$).

In terms of mediating effects: Learning engagement had a significant mediating effect on career engagement through departmental identity ($\beta = .245^*$, $*p < .05$). Learning engagement also had a significant mediating effect on career engagement through career self-efficacy ($\beta = .218^*$, $*p < .05$). For the explanatory variance of the model: The variance explained by departmental

identity was 30.4%. The variance explained by career self-efficacy was 43.5%. The variance explained by career engagement was 49.3%. Overall, the model in this study demonstrated good explanatory power.

Figure 2: Structural Model Analysis Results of Students' Learning Engagement, Departmental Identity, Career Self-Efficacy, and Career Engagement

CONCLUSION

Practical Contributions

Whether students in sports-related departments have a strong sense of identity with their department and interest in the sports and leisure industry will guide them to enter the sports and leisure industry workplace after graduation.

If students can make career plans during their studies, enhance their departmental identity and learning engagement, and improve their career self-efficacy, they will be able to smoothly connect with the workplace after graduation and invest more effort in their work. This will help attract more outstanding talents to the sports and leisure industry.

Theoretical Contributions

This study used the "Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) Model" to explore the relationships among learning engagement, departmental identity, career self-efficacy, and career engagement of students in Taiwan's sports and leisure-related departments.

A review of relevant literature shows that the S-O-R Model is mainly used to study consumers' consumption behavior. This study attempted to apply the S-O-R Model to explore students' future career engagement behavior and found that the model is highly consistent with the study's theoretical hypotheses: learning engagement (Stimulus) positively affects career engagement (Response) through the mediating factors of departmental identity and career self-

efficacy (Organism). In other words, when students engage in sports industry-related learning, strengthening their departmental identity and personal career self-efficacy will increase the probability of their future engagement in the related industry. Therefore, this study believes it has made a new theoretical discovery regarding the S-O-R Model: the model can not only be used to study consumers' consumption behavior but also to research students' future career engagement.

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